

CHARACTERISTIC APPEARANCES OF LEGAL NIHILISM OBSERVED IN SOCIAL AREAS

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Annotation: This article describes a number of specific manifestations of legal nihilism observed in the social sphere today, as well as methods for eliminating it.

Keywords: social sphere, Society, legal consciousness, legal nihilism, law, disdain.

Legal nihilism is one of the negative phenomena that seriously threatens the systematic and purposeful development of the legal development of society and hinders the growth of legal consciousness and legal culture. Nihilism (derived from the Latin word “nihil”, meaning - nothing, - negation). Legal nihilism means the negative attitude of individuals, social groups to certain legal values, norms, established procedures, disregard and rejection of any norms, principles and laws, and expresses the negative attitude of the subject to certain values, norms, views, ideals, certain aspects of human life, and sometimes all aspects. Nihilism is one of the forms of perception of the world and social behavior. Nihilism can take on moral, legal, political, ideological nihilism, and other forms, depending on what values are rejected and what area of knowledge and social practice is being discussed - culture, law, morality .

In the case of legal nihilism, laws are not applied, they are openly violated, not enforced, not valued, not respected. Legal nihilism is a phenomenon that hinders the development of legal consciousness and legal culture. In countries where anarchism has reached its peak, anarchism and extremism are combined.

Two main reasons for legal nihilism can be identified. The first reason is that for many years an undemocratic regime has prevailed in our country, that is, state activity is not based on law. The second reason is that for many years the understanding of law as a norm has prevailed, and therefore law has been associated with the will of the state. In other words, law is the dominant expression of the will of the state, and any normative document is in harmony with the command of the state, which has led to a negative attitude towards law and an active denial of law. There are various forms of expression of legal nihilism.

Today, a weak legal nihilism is mainly manifested. That is, there are cases of disregard for existing legal norms and indifference to laws by people in society.

Nihilism, one of the forms of social behavior, means the denial of the existing social form of life and moral norms, cultural heritage and ideals. Denial is a common sign of all forms of nihilism. Today, there are various manifestations of legal nihilism in social spheres. Social spheres include such areas as public education, healthcare, art and culture, science, physical education and sports, scientific research, public administration, defense, and household services. Without them, the development of society is impossible to imagine. Because the general direction of the work of employees in this field is aimed at the social and spiritual development of man and society .

It is clear from this that by increasing legal knowledge and literacy among young people, we can eliminate legal nihilism. To interest them in law, to make them understand their rights, duties, and obligations should be considered the most important issue today. The formation of legal immunity in the younger generation against factors that negatively affect their legal education, the instilling in each person a sense of respect for laws and morals, loyalty to national values, and intolerance towards violations of law are of particular importance today.

We all need to feel that the effectiveness of our reforms lies in the full and creative fulfillment of their duties by responsible employees and specialists in educational institutions, legal education and advocacy.

Not only in the field of education, but also in the fields of healthcare, science, art and culture, there are a number of manifestations of legal nihilism. In particular, in the healthcare sector, the Ministry of Justice announced a legal campaign "Protecting the rights of healthcare and education system employees" from March 15 to May 15, 2022, to eliminate legal nihilism towards doctors and increase the legal literacy of employees in the sector.

More than 1,530 promotional events were carried out by justice bodies to increase the legal literacy of employees in the sector. In particular, 9 appearances were made on television channels and 55 on the radio, 13 articles were published in newspapers and magazines, more than 600 seminars and roundtable discussions were held, and information was posted on websites and social networks more than 760 times.

Also, within the framework of the campaign, 2,285 appeals were received by the justice authorities in the field, of which 1,386 (64.4%) were satisfied,

legal explanations were provided for 387 appeals, and 21 appeals were forwarded to the competent authorities as appropriate.

In our country, a lot of work has been done to inform citizens about the laws and improve their legal culture: active lecture and publishing work is still being carried out with the involvement of legal scholars, practitioners of law enforcement agencies, and legal consultants. Today, the participation of lawyers in legal education and legal advocacy is practically not considered their official duty. Legal advocacy and legal education can also be carried out by explaining current legislation to the public, providing advice on it with the direct participation of lawyers, giving lectures, speaking in the press, on television and radio.

Today, it is especially important to form legal immunity in the younger generation against factors that negatively affect their legal education, to instill in each person a sense of respect for laws and morals, loyalty to national values, and intolerance towards violations.

We all need to feel that the effectiveness of our reforms lies in the full and creative fulfillment of their duties by responsible employees and specialists in educational institutions, legal education and advocacy.

Significant work is being carried out in our country to fundamentally reform the national legal system, form a legal culture in society, and train qualified legal personnel. At the same time, special attention is paid to forming an attitude of respect for human rights and freedoms, raising the legal consciousness and legal culture of young people, increasing the level of legal literacy of citizens in society, and eliminating legal nihilism. Only when young people understand the essence of the concepts of legal consciousness and culture, they understand their rights and obligations.

In conclusion, it should be noted that in order to increase the legal awareness and legal literacy of people working in social spheres and young people, to eliminate legal nihilism in them, to form a serious approach to current events, not a passive one, it is necessary to increase law classes in educational institutions, to introduce interesting legal shows and programs in the media, including television. It is necessary to introduce young students studying law in higher educational institutions to talk to students in secondary schools, and even to attend school classes. Only then can we eliminate legal nihilism among our youth.

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